

ECTOPIC PREGNANCY TREATMENT METHODS AND
RISK FACTORS FOR LIFE

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Abstract. An ectopic pregnancy is a condition in which a fertilized egg implants and develops outside the uterus, usually in the fallopian tube. However, sometimes an ectopic pregnancy can develop in the ovary, cervix, or abdominal cavity. This scientific article discusses treatment and diagnostic methods and possible complications.

Keywords: ectopic pregnancy, abortion, fallopian tube rupture, peritonitis, hypovolemic shock, ovarian cysts, endometriosis, chorion.

Materials and methods: In this work, modern scientific literature has been studied and analyzed, as well as the works of specialists in this industry.

Results: An ectopic pregnancy occurs when the fertilized egg fails to reach the uterine cavity or when the egg moves in the wrong direction. This may occur due to problems with the structure or function of the fallopian tube, inflammatory diseases, previous pelvic surgery, hormonal changes, or other medical conditions.

An ectopic pregnancy is unacceptable and requires immediate medical intervention, as it can lead to rupture of the tube, bleeding, and other serious complications for the woman's health, including death. Treatment for ectopic pregnancy may include surgical removal of the embryo or the use of drugs that can cause the embryo to be reabsorbed or expelled from the body.

Complications: An ectopic pregnancy can be life-threatening and require urgent medical attention. Some life-threatening conditions that can occur with an ectopic pregnancy include:

1 . Fallopian tube rupture: One of the most serious complications of an ectopic pregnancy is a ruptured tube, which can lead to internal bleeding. This condition requires immediate surgical intervention to stop bleeding and remove the ectopic pregnancy.

2 . Bleeding from an ectopic pregnancy: An ectopic pregnancy can cause bleeding, especially if there is a ruptured fallopian tube or other complications. Severe bleeding can result in blood loss and, in some cases, shock and life-threatening conditions for the patient.

3 . Peritonitis: A ruptured ectopic pregnancy can lead to internal bleeding and infection, which can cause peritonitis, an inflammation of the peritoneum (the lining that covers the abdominal organs). Peritonitis is a serious and life-threatening condition requiring urgent surgical intervention and antibiotics.

4 . Hypovolemic shock: Heavy bleeding caused by a ruptured ectopic pregnancy can lead to hypovolemic shock, a condition in which cardiac function is reduced due to significant blood loss. Hypovolemic shock requires urgent resuscitation measures, including restoration of circulating blood volume and blood supply to organs.

Differential diagnosis: Ectopic pregnancy involves identifying and excluding other possible pathological conditions that may mimic the symptoms of an ectopic pregnancy. Some of these conditions include:

1. Missed period: Missed period can be due to various reasons, including pregnancy. Therefore, the first step in diagnosing an ectopic pregnancy is to confirm or rule out the presence of pregnancy using pregnancy tests.

2. Abortion: Some types of abortion can mimic the symptoms of an ectopic pregnancy. For example, if the placenta is prematurely rejected, you may also experience vaginal bleeding, soreness, and low blood pressure. However, during an abortion, there is usually no level of human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) in the blood, which is usually elevated in an ectopic pregnancy.

3. Gastrointestinal diseases: Some gastrointestinal diseases, such as appendicitis, stomach ulcers, or intestinal obstruction, can cause pain in the lower abdomen, similar to symptoms of an ectopic pregnancy. However, in these cases, there are usually no other symptoms of pregnancy, such as a missed period or a positive pregnancy test.

4. Gynecological processes: Some gynecological diseases, such as ovarian cysts, inflammatory processes, or endometriosis, can mimic the symptoms of an ectopic pregnancy. As in previous cases, confirmation or exclusion of pregnancy is the first step in differential diagnosis.

5. Intrauterine Mesh: In some rare cases, breast mesh (intrauterine contraceptive device) can cause symptoms similar to an ectopic pregnancy. This can usually be avoided with an ultrasound examination.

Types of treatment: There are several methods of surgical treatment for ectopic pregnancy, and the choice of method depends on various factors, such as the size and location of the ectopic pregnancy, the woman's condition, and the doctor's preference.

1. Laparoscopic salpingostomy: This is a minimally invasive approach that uses laparoscopic equipment to insert instruments through small incisions in the abdomen. The doctor makes a small incision in the fallopian tube to remove the embryo and save the tube.

2. Laparoscopic salpingectomy: In this case, the fallopian tube is completely removed. This may be necessary if the pipe is severely damaged or is at risk of bursting.

3. Laparotomy: This is a more invasive surgery in which the doctor makes a larger incision in the abdomen to gain access to the internal organs. The external incision is usually made vertically along the midline of the abdomen. Laparotomy may be necessary if the ectopic pregnancy is large or other complications exist.

4. Embryectomy by Hysteroscopy: In some cases, when an ectopic pregnancy develops in the uterine cavity or cervix, a procedure may be performed to remove the embryo using hysteroscopy. The hysteroscope is inserted into the uterine cavity through the cervix and the embryo is removed or destroyed using instruments.

Factors: When choosing a method of surgical treatment for ectopic pregnancy, the doctor takes into account several factors:

1. Location of ectopic pregnancy: If the embryo is in the fallopian tube, then methods of preserving or removing only this tube are possible. If an ectopic pregnancy develops elsewhere, such as in the ovary, the organ may be removed or preserved.

2. Size and condition of ectopic pregnancy: Large or complicated ectopic pregnancies may require more invasive removal techniques or removal of the affected organ. Smaller and uncomplicated ectopic pregnancies can be successfully removed using a less invasive procedure.

3. Patient's reproductive plans: If a woman plans to maintain the possibility of future pregnancy, the doctor may prefer a method that helps preserve healthy tissue and tubes.

4. General Condition of the Patient: If the woman has other medical problems or complications, closer monitoring or more invasive treatments may be required.

5. Skills and preferences of the doctor: The doctor chooses the method based on his experience, skills, and preferences, taking into account all the above factors.

Discussions: Summarizing this work, it is worth highlighting that the tactics and treatment algorithm depend on such factors as the location of the ectopic pregnancy, the size, and condition of the ectopic pregnancy, the patient's reproductive plans, general condition, doctor's skills, as

well as the degree of invasiveness, the likelihood of complications and treatment methods, which emphasizes the importance careful approach of the doctor to this disease.

Conclusions: After analyzing this work, we can summarize that the treatment of ectopic pregnancy depends on many factors, from the patient's reproductive plans and the personal skills of the doctor to the diagnostic method and the general condition of the patient, which may contradict a certain treatment method. Ectopic pregnancy should be treated immediately; therefore, the diagnostic method and type of treatment should be carefully selected by the attending physician to avoid complications, iatrogenicity, and threats to life.

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